

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE MICROTEACHING METHOD IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEAKING SKILL IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This study was carried out in order to test the effectiveness of the microteaching method on student success and its permanence effect in this success compared to that of the traditional method in the development of the pronunciation skill in a foreign language. This effect was tested on the access levels related to the 'realization of the pronunciation skill' potential. Additionally, it was aimed to determine whether the preservation of the pronunciation skill access levels varies depending on the method used in teaching the skill or not. The methods used in teaching are the teaching and traditional teaching methods carried out with videos and tapes, which are two forms of microteaching. Moreover, the effect of these different methods on the permanence of the skill was investigated. The study was designed and carried out according to the 'Solomon four group model'. 40 students in the I-K class taking the 'English I Program' in Eskişehir Süleyman Çakır High School in the first semester of 1993-1994 academic year participated in the study. Using the random method in the formation of groups, four groups were determined with 10 students in each, and two of which were experimental and two were control groups. Since this study aims to determine the effectiveness of a teaching method (independent variable), experiment and control groups were tried to be equalized in terms of variables other than the method. At the end of the equalization process, 40 students were equalized and distributed to the groups. In order to collect the data, a 'Pronunciation Skill Test' and a related "evaluation form" were prepared. The test material was a part of the English I Program that students participating in the research were taking. The test of pronunciation skill was carried out with a form that measures the correct pronunciation of 15 words with values between 1 and 5. This form was applied as a pretest-posttest in the study. This form was applied as a pretest to one of each two groups, experiment and control groups. As a result of the pretest, it was shown statistically that the groups did not differ from each other and the teaching was carried

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out by the microteaching method for the two experimental groups and by the traditional method for the two control groups. Two different forms of the microteaching method (Video-Tape) were applied to two experimental groups. These practices were carried only on the pronunciation skill and took place within a week. After the teaching of the skill was completed within the context of the content, all groups were post tested. One month after obtaining the pretest and posttest results for the experimental and control groups, the permanence of the skill was investigated. By analyzing whether the methods differ in terms of permanence, the data were started to be analyzed. In the analysis of the data, comparisons between the groups were made by calculating the standard deviations of the mean scores and score distributions of the groups. In these comparisons, t test was used and it was interpreted at 0,001 and 0,05 significance level. The effectiveness of the experimental processes was interpreted by taking the score differences between intra-groups and inter-groups and the significance of these differences into consideration.

Keywords: microteaching method, development of speaking skill, foreign language education

1. Introduction

The developing technology and the accumulation of knowledge led societies to be in a closer relationship. These relationships gradually called forth bilateral, tripartite agreements, continental unions, universal organizations and made foreign language learning more and more necessary (Demirel, 1999, p.5). However, languages learned as foreign languages are not chosen randomly, their numbers are few and they are learned or taught depending on some criteria. Economic and political advantages have priority over these criteria. Military conventions, historical, cultural, and commercial relations, art and technology are preference criteria for learning languages.

Sözer (1984), who considers foreign language education as inevitable to keep up with the era, emphasizes the need for foreign language education in order to catch up with the advancement of science, technique and communication at a great pace and to catch up with the modern civilization. As a country trying to catch up with the era, Turkey practices and attaches importance to foreign language education. The most prominent of these languages is English (Demirel, 1990). Students learn English in many secondary education institutions. Yaşar says that the need to learn a foreign language in Turkey entered into laws and development plans and ranked among the objectives to be achieved (1990, p.2). Özer (1984) stressed the need to establish a foreign language education system that is in accordance with the country's needs and that has a scientific basis and the need to realize a good level of foreign language education in Turkey.

Various approaches must be used for an effective foreign language education. As a result of the emergence of various approaches in foreign language education in the world, the establishment of a new world order especially after World War II and political developments, the importance of learning foreign language was increased and an

increase has been recorded in learning the languages of countries with economic and political superiority.

For a long time, the traditional Grammar and Translation Method was used in foreign language teaching, but after 1930s, a tendency that the language of speech was gaining weight was observed. This method, named as direct method, lost its effectiveness with the development of the audio-lingual habit method later on (Özer, 1978). Afterwards, communicative method emerged, and more rational and flexible, multidirectional language education theory was developed instead of behavioral approach (Demirel, 1994, p.44, Kılıç, 1980, p.88).

Later, another approach known as LSP (Language for Specific Purpose) was introduced. These methods based on the principle of usefulness in foreign language education came into play as a more limited and useful approach where needs were taken into consideration (Sözer, 1979, p.16). The arrangement of foreign language teaching for conceptual, individual, situational and communicative and functional purposes emerged as a result of this change (Koç, 1979).

In the light of all this, in foreign language education, goals should be determined first and after deciding which language skill to acquire to what extent, the path to be followed should be decided by selecting the approach (Demircan, 1988, p.168).

In foreign language education, the theoretical bases are few and the choice of the path to be followed can be determined depending on the philosophy adopted. When practical qualities are desired in addition to grammar knowledge, training requires a better selection and planning.

As a result, today there is no mention of a universal method in foreign language education. It is stated that the relationship with mother tongue, priorities in learning and adaptation to country conditions affect success (Erçoban, 1979).

There have always been problems in foreign language education in Turkey. The first of these problems is the teaching method problem arising from the system. Countries that are the source of the languages learned as foreign languages also determine the methods and techniques. Moreover, foreign language education, which is habitual and gives information about language, is seen among other important problems (Cited by Işık, 2008).

Yule (2006) examines foreign language education as learning and acquiring foreign languages. Foreign language acquisition explains how to use a language actively with all aspects. However, communication problems are experienced in foreign language learning.

Foreign language education is actually a program problem. This problem should be solved based on basic research or applied research producing information. In this way, education processes can be improved. Unless development is based on research findings, the solution of problems seems unlikely (Varış, 1978). Only a program and program development studies that are suitable for changing conditions and constantly renew themselves will contribute to and lead to foreign language education (Soytekin, 1979).

In secondary education institutions in Turkey, foreign language education was carried out mostly for cognitive purposes and it focused mostly on grammar. This prevents the use of language. Although it is necessary to practice goal-oriented method in foreign language education, this method is not given much weight in practice (Bayraktaroğlu, 1979, p.10; Sebüktekin, 1978, p.10). Effective ways should be used to achieve effective education especially for high school students. Today, students are interested in technology and communication and use it frequently. It is known that using these ways and tools in foreign language education will lead to more permanent results. There is a need for research results that will provide improvement in this subject, too (Alkan, 1984, p.56).

When the way to learn basic skills in foreign language education is examined, it is accepted that it is not different from native language learning (Cem, 1979, p.70). People learn to listen by listening, to speak by speaking, to read by reading, and to write by writing. In today's techniques, this approach is adopted. Naturally, listening and speaking activities begin first in language learning and then reading and writing skills develop. Then it would be appropriate to follow a natural approach in foreign language education. (Cem, 1979, p.70). Language teaching can be functional only when it provides acquisition of these four basic skills. Listening and reading skills are grouped as 'acquisition skills' and speaking and writing skills are grouped as 'production skills' (Yaşar, 1993, p.4). Listening and reading is about 'understanding' and speaking, and writing are about 'narration'. The aim of listening is to recognize the voices in the language, to notice the change in meaning where the emphasis differs and to ensure that the message is perceived correctly. With reading skills, students are expected to make sense of what they read and to receive the message given by the author. Writing skills mean that students can express their feelings and thoughts in writing. Here, it is important to be able to perceive the rules of language here. Speaking skills require students to learn some of the non-verbal behaviors as well as the language and way of speaking. Speaking skills require students to learn some non-verbal behaviors as well as the rules and pronunciation of language.

While it is widely accepted to follow the natural way in developing four basic skills in foreign language education, practices focusing on goal-oriented skills have intensified in recent years as well (Yaşar, 1993, p.4). However, it is both wrong and unlikely to isolate four basic skills in foreign language education. Therefore, a rational way to follow would be to develop these skills together, but mainly for the purpose. For example, while developing the reading skill, 70% weight can be given to this skill, 20% on listening and speaking and 10% on writing, because a person who wants to explain what he reads in writing or verbally will have to use both speaking and writing skills (Demirel, 1990, p.107).

Although all four of these skills are intended to be acquired in secondary education, education is mostly directed towards cognitive goals. For example, although one of the goals is "*understands someone who speaks at normal speed and speaks the language*

at normal speed”, a person who is a graduate of high school cannot achieve the goal especially in terms of speech.

There are behaviors related to ‘the pronunciation skill’ in every subject in 2018 MEB (the Ministry of National Education, Turkey) Secondary Education English Teaching Program (MEB, 2018). This shows that the pronunciation skill should not be neglected in any lesson.

Speaking skill is commonly used both in education and social life. A large part of daily life is listening and speaking. Therefore, it is stated that speaking skill is more important in learning a foreign language than other skills (Emiroğlu, 2013, p.277).

Pronunciation takes place in the basis of speech. In determining the development of students on this subject, the need to include their own and peers’ views and opinions is emphasized (Göçer, 2015, p.49). In determining the development of speaking skill, students' ability to show their speaking skills is evaluated. The method to be used for this is monitoring and observation. Observation can be used as a complementary assessment in individual and group activities (Bahar et al., 2012).

One of the exercises that foreign language teachers use most in developing speaking skills in secondary education are mechanical exercises (such as displacement). Pronunciation is the way of saying words and sounds. Language learning starts with uttering sounds and speaking words in that language. Pronunciation practice is applied at the first levels in foreign language education. It is important that sounds and words are not pronounced incorrectly, pronunciation practice is included, and mistakes are corrected and understood (Demirel, 1990, p.114). In such a case, it would be useful to use technology. One of the applications of Educational Technologies, which can be analyzed in a mass and individual dimension, is Microteaching (Hızal, 1993, p.44). Today, the importance of individual-sized technologies is increasing day by day. So, the idea that ‘microteaching’ can be used as an appropriate way to improve pronunciation skill arises when it is necessary both to choose appropriate research-based methods and to benefit from technology.

It is not seen necessary to allocate a lot of time to teaching pronunciation in foreign language lessons. The pronunciation skill includes listening, identification, recognition, utterance and correcting stages. These skills are considered important, but it is emphasized that they should be developed without wasting much time. In this case, the need to create a good analysis, method and technology arises. Using the possibilities of technology will also contribute here. Micro-teaching is a teaching experiment that is reduced in terms of duration, number of students, and content (Alkan, 1991, p.117). The method can be applied both with and without video/audio (tape).

Microteaching brings a new understanding in terms of concentration of attention on model (teacher) behavior, preparation of an environment for controlled study and behavior analysis (Alkan, 1987, p. 24).

Microteaching is the teaching system that enables to review students’ reaction immediately and later by video, thereby provides the effect that is otherwise impossible (Knapper, 1980, p.35).

In education, it is an effective way to record student performances in order to re-watch what is done and make evaluation analysis (Brown & Lewis, 1977, p.258). These records can be evaluated individually or in groups later on. Image, sound or both can be used. Microteaching is a method that can be used effectively in Sports, Local Speaking, Music, Drama etc. areas.

Based on Bandura's "Social Learning Theory", Microteaching gives students the opportunity to monitor the realization of a certain skill in a small learning situation. Thus, learning is realized by imitating the sample. Considering all aspects, it seems to be one of the application methods of behavioral theories, but it tries to provide a more balanced synthesis of 'Cognitive Psychology' with Bandura's Social Learning and Skinner's Behavioral Theory (Gordon and Hillgard, 1975, p.461).

2. Microteaching

Microteaching is a method that was initially introduced to enable prospective teachers to apply and improve their teaching skills in a risk-free classroom-like environment or in a real classroom environment (Banerjee, 2015). It was developed by Dwight Allen at Stanford University in 1950s and 1960s (Yusuf, 2006). This method was reconsidered and simplified in 1980s and 1990s. In fact, the method is based on making prospective teacher focus on one skill at a time and master it. The skill is improved by repeating the same skill and receiving the feedback of the counselor and the support of his peers. Prospective teachers plan and apply the skill for different scenarios. In fact, Microteaching is the development of the same skill with the support and feedback received many times.

In this case, the pronunciation skill in foreign language education can be thought of as students' accomplishment a skill they do not dare and are afraid of doing wrong among the close peer group and by watching the model.

Microteaching is an applied technology used in controlled situations. The content to be learned should be reduced to simplify. In this method, attention is focused on a certain skill, the number of students can be 4-7 and it lasts 5-10 minutes. Microteaching environment is a real classroom environment that is reduced in number and duration (Sayan, 1994). The real benefit of the student who performs the skill is 'feedback'. Feedback can be in different forms in Microteaching and plays the main role. The student's exercise can be recorded in video, audio, or both. At the end of the exercise, the peers in the group and the teacher focus on the positive aspects so that the evaluation is in objective conditions and the errors are corrected next time (Rıza, 1990, p.148).

Social Learning Theory is a mixture that analyzes the learning, motivation and reinforcement of cognitive behaviorism and includes the effects of external events. Thus, it is a modern theory that will be effective in solving a practical problem.

One way to teach people behavior in an applied service is through observation. The probability of initiating the behavior can be increased by making people observe (Gordon and Hillgard, 1975, p. 472). The pronunciation skill in foreign language education can also be improved through observation and imitation. Microteaching goes

through several successive stages, too. These stages are like examining the skill, watching the model or video, performing the skill, evaluation, and development (Perrot, 1977, p.31).

Microteaching is a method used in teacher training institutions in many countries of the world (Külahçı, 1994, p.13). It can be performed with or without a tool, but UNESCO recommended developing countries to practice it without a tool (Gürkan, 1991, p.69.).

Külahçı investigated the usability of microteaching in Turkey and stated that it can be used at all levels, starting from preschool, in evaluating programs such as teacher training, teacher selection, and in-service training of teachers, in developing teaching skills, in creating teaching models and to develop teaching materials (1994). The tools used in microteaching are microphones, cameras, mixers, videotapes, monitors.

However, in today's technology there are technologies taking the place of them. Even easier and more efficient use can be achieved only with smartphones, smart boards or social media tools. It can be performed without tools as well as with the technology available.

Educational benefits of microteaching can be listed as follows. In addition to simplifying the learning practice, developing skills, taking feedback, using models, practicing, using equipment, achieving success, developing a positive attitude towards the profession, it also increases students' self-confidence (Allen & Ryan, 1969, p.62). If the resources are limited, it has benefits such as the possibility of conducting controlled trials and filling the gap of those who cannot attend the classes (Gürkan, 1991, Rıza, 1990, Hızal, 1993).

Microteaching may come in for criticism. Issues such as not being able to analyze or reduce every learning practice, difficulties in finding and using tools, and cost impose restriction on the usage of it.

A lot of studies have been done on micro education. The vast majority of these studies are about teaching skills. In this study, the use of 'the Microteaching Method' and 'the Traditional Teaching Method' is compared in the development of the pronunciation skill, which is included in the speaking skill in a foreign language, and it is tried to reveal whether there is a difference in terms of student success.

3. Method

In this part of the study, the study model, the population and the sample, the creation of experimental and control groups, the data collection tools, and the statistical methods and techniques used to collect data and analyze the collected data were explained.

3.1 Study Model

This study, which aims to test the effectiveness of the 'microteaching' method in the development of the pronunciation skill, which is one of the speaking skills in foreign

language, was designed and carried out according to 'Solomon four group model' which is one of the real experiment models.

3.2 Population and Sample

The population of this study, which is experimental, consists of 416 students studying English I Program at Eskişehir Süleyman Çakır High School in the first semester of 1993-1994 Academic Year. In the sample of the study, there are 40 students from I-K class who received the same program in the same period.

3.3 Data Collection Tools and Data Collection

A **questionnaire** to collect the data deemed necessary to answer the sub-problems of the research and an **equalization test** used together with it were prepared and a **list of target behaviors and behavioral goals** related to the pronunciation skill was created. Additionally, a **skill assessment form** was prepared to evaluate students' pronunciation of each word. This form was used in conjunction with the **content** as an equalization test.

According to the results of the questionnaire and the equalization test, the class was divided into four equivalent groups, each consisting of ten students without teaching the pronunciation of the words. In obtaining this equivalence, both personal information and equalization test results were taken into consideration.

Before the experiment, the behavioral goals list was prepared and given to the teachers and fifteen new words in this list were divided into three groups, each group included five words. Each time different teachers uttered the words in each group, used them in sentences and they were recorded on video and tape. While the control groups were watching the normal lesson in the classroom, tape and video groups watched and listened to the models in separate places. The groups were also informed beforehand of what they would do. Behavioral goals were also listed and given to them.

After the students in the video group watched the models, the students were asked to pronounce these words. Again, in groups of five, words were pronounced by the students three times and during the realization of the skill, they were recorded on video tape. Upon completion of the record, students gathered with their advisors (teachers), watched how they and their friends performed the skill and received feedback. The positive aspects were emphasized most and for the wrongs, it was said to watch the models again. When correct pronunciation was obtained, the process was not continued. Students in the Tape Group followed the same way with the tape by listening to the sounds.

After completing the teaching of the students in the classroom with the traditional method and the experimental groups with microteaching, all students were post-tested and the results were recorded in the evaluation form. The evaluation was transferred to charts by taking the mean of the grades given by three English teachers

One of the questions asked in the study is "What is the effect of microteaching in terms of permanence of student success compared to the traditional teaching?" For this reason, the pronunciation skill test, which was applied to the students as pretest-posttest,

was re-administered one month after the first application and re-evaluated by the same teachers according to the evaluation form.

3.4 Data Analysis

In the evaluation of the experimental subjects, the mean values of the scores given by the three different teachers were used. Here, the mean values were calculated manually by the researcher.

After obtaining the pretest, posttest and permanence test results of the experimental and control groups, the groups' mean scores and the standard deviations of the score distributions were calculated.

T-test was used in comparisons between groups and the significance of the difference between the score means of the groups was interpreted at the level of 0,01.

In the analysis of study data;

- 1) One-way variance analysis was used to test the equivalence of the groups before the experiment.
- 2) Arithmetic mean was used in relation to the scores of the groups.
- 3) In independent samples, t value related to the significance of the difference between arithmetic means was examined.
- 4) When comparing conjugate samples, t value was calculated.

$$t = \frac{\bar{D}}{SD}, \bar{D} = \frac{SD}{N}, SD = \frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{n}}{(n-1).n} \text{ formulas were used.}$$

The processing and analysis of the data were carried out on ETACOMP 386 computers and MINITAB package program was used for statistical operations.

4. Findings and Comments

The principle of 'internal compliance' (Captain; 1977, p. 242) was followed in presenting the findings and comments. Findings and comments regarding the sub-problems addressed in this order are as follows:

A. In the first sub-problem of the study, "Determining whether there is a significant difference in terms of student success between the microteaching method and the traditional teaching method in the development of the pronunciation skill in a foreign language" is aimed.

Table 1: Findings Regarding Pronunciation Skill
 Video and Control Groups Pretest Scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G1 Video	10	18,30	2,710	0,287	18	0,05
G2 Control I	10	18,60	1,647			

t: Table 2,10

Here, there is no significant difference between the pre-experimental status of the students in the video and Control I groups in terms of the pronunciation skill in a foreign language.

Based on these findings, in order to determine the effectiveness of video-based microteaching, the pronunciation skill pretest and posttest scores of the students in the video group were compared and the findings are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Findings regarding pronunciation skill
 video group pretest and posttest scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G1 Pretest	10	18,300	2,7	59,57	9	<0,001
G2 Posttest	10	73,900	0,876			

t:Table 4,781

This result reveals that the microteaching method applied by video is effective in terms of students' acquiring the pronunciation skill.

In order to determine the effect of the microteaching method, the mean scores of one of the experiment groups (G1 Video) and one of the control groups (G, Control I) the pronunciation skill posttest scores were examined.

Table 3: Findings regarding pronunciation skill
 video group posttest and control i group posttest scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G1 Video	10	73,900	0,876	6,84	18	<0,001
G2 Control	10	69,200	1,990			

t:Table 4,318

The result shows us that the microteaching method realized with video may be more effective than the traditional method in acquiring the pronunciation skill.

Again, in determining the effect of the method experienced, the posttest scores regarding the pronunciation skill of students in one of the experimental groups (Tape G)

and one of the control groups (Control II G4) were compared. Related findings are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Findings regarding tape group posttest and control II group posttest scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G3 Tape	10	72,50	2,17	3,13	18	<0,001
G4 Control	10	64,30	8,00			

t:Table 2,878

According to this result, it can be said that the microteaching method applied by using tape in order to acquire the pronunciation skill in a foreign language is more effective than the traditional method.

Another comparison was made between one of the experimental groups (Tape G3) and one of the control groups (Control I G2) to determine the effectiveness of the method. In this comparison, the mean scores of the scores the students in the tape group got from the posttest related to the pronunciation skill and the scores the students in the Control I Group got from the pretest were examined. These findings are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Findings regarding pronunciation skill tape group posttest and control I group pretest scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G3 Tape	10	72,500	2,17	62,52	18	<0,001
G4 Control	10	18,600	1,65			

t:Table 3,922

This result reveals that there is a significant difference between the posttest mean score of the group for whom microteaching was applied and the pretest mean score of the group for whom the traditional method was applied in acquiring the pronunciation skill. In other words, microteaching with tape was more effective than the traditional method.

In order to determine the effectiveness of the method, another comparison was made between the pretest mean score of one of the experimental groups (video) related to the pronuncial skill and the posttest mean score of one of the control groups (G4 Control II).

Table 6: Findings regarding video group pretest and control II group posttest scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G1 Video	10	18,30	2,71	17,22	18	<0,001
G4 Control II	10	64,30	8,00			

t:Table 3,92

This result shows that the microteaching method performed by video is effective in terms of student success in acquiring the pronunciation skill.

In order to determine the effectiveness of the Microteaching method in acquiring the pronunciation skill, another comparison was made by looking at the difference between pretest mean score of Control I Group students and posttest mean score of Control II students. This difference is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Findings regarding control II group posttest and control I group pretest scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G4 Control II	10	64,30	8,00	17,69	18	<0,05
G2 Control	10	18,60	1,65			

t:Table 2,101

This result shows that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest applied to the groups. In other words, the traditional teaching method was effective in students' acquiring the pronunciation skill.

B. In the second sub-problem of the study, it was aimed to determine "Whether there is a significant difference in terms of student success between microteaching using videotape and microteaching using tape in the development of the pronunciation skill in a foreign language." For this purpose, the posttest mean scores of the groups equalized with questionnaire and equalization test were compared. Thus, it was aimed to determine which of the two practices tried on the same groups was more effective.

Table 8: Findings regarding video and tape groups posttest mean scores

Student Groups	Number of Experimental Subjects (N)	Arithmetic Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T	Degree of Freedom (Df)	Significance Level (P)
G1 Video	10	73,90	0,88	1,89	18	>0,05
G3 Tape	10	72,50	2,17			

t:Table 2,10

According to the result, there is no significant difference between the posttest mean scores of the Video and Tape groups as a result of microteaching practices. The effectiveness of microteaching practices on groups is close to each other.

C. In the third sub-problem of the study, it was aimed to determine "Whether there is a difference in terms of permanence of skill between experimental and control groups at the end of the practices of acquiring the pronunciation skill in a foreign language with the microteaching method or the traditional method."

For this purpose, it was tried to determine the difference between the difference the posttest and permanence test mean scores, where the Video and Tape groups were

considered as 'Experimental group' together, and the difference between the posttest and permanence test mean scores, where the Control I and Control II groups were considered as the 'Control Group'.

Table 9: Findings regarding the difference of the differences of mean scores of the experimental groups (video-tape) and the control groups (control I-control II) posttest and permanence test

Experimental Groups			Control Groups			
Posttest	Kal Test	Posttest Kal T. Difference	Posttest	Permanence Test	Posttest Kal T. Difference	Mean Score Difference of Difference
N ₁ =20	N ₂ =20		N ₃ =20	N ₄ =20		
X ₁ =73,25	X ₂ =73,75	0,50	X ₃ =66,95	X ₄ =66,25	1,70	1,60
SS ₁ =177	SS ₂ =1,41		SS ₃ =6,14	SS ₄ =6,23		

T Calculation: 3,13 > t Table:2,704 Sd:38 P <0,05

According to the table, the pronunciation skill acquired in foreign language with the method of microteaching is more permanent than the skill acquired by the traditional method.

D. In the fourth sub-problem of the study, it was aimed to determine "Whether there is a difference in terms of student success between video microteaching and tape microteaching performed for permanence of the pronunciation skill in a foreign language."

Table 10: Findings regarding the difference of the differences between video and tape groups pronunciation skill posttest and permanence test mean scores and these mean scores

Video			Tape			
Posttest	Kal Test	Posttest Kal T. Difference	Posttest	Permanence Test	Posttest Kal T. Difference	Mean Score Difference of Difference
N ₁ =10	N ₂ =10	0,000	N ₃ =10	N ₄ =10		
X ₁ =74,200	X ₂ =74,200		X ₃ =72,600	X ₄ =73,300	-0,700	-0,700
SS ₁ =0,789	SS ₂ =0,632		SS ₃ =2,221	SS ₄ =1,829		

t Calculation: 1,209 t Table:2,101 Sd:18 P>0,05

According to the table, no significant difference was found between the permanence of the pronunciation skill achieved as a result of the microteaching practice performed with the video, and the permanence of the pronunciation skill achieved as a result of the microteaching performed with tape. However, the results obtained reveal the view that by increasing the number of experimental subjects, more accurate findings can be reached and perhaps a difference can be revealed.

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

In the light of the findings revealed in the research, it was concluded that micro teaching method is more effective than traditional teaching method in developing foreign language speaking skills. However, it is considered necessary to conduct other sensitive experiments on the subject.

With the second sub-problem of the research, it is aimed to determine whether there is a meaningful difference in terms of student achievement between micro-teaching using video and using tape in the development of speaking skills in a foreign language. As a result of micro education applications with Video and Tape, there is no significant difference between the posttest mean scores. The effectiveness of micro education applications on groups findings were found to be close to each other.

In the third sub-problem of the research, it is aimed to determine whether there is a difference between the experimental and control groups in terms of permanence of the skill at the end of the practice of gaining the skill of speaking in foreign language with the method of "micro teaching" or "traditional method". The level reached by experimental groups in terms of speaking skill has not decreased much over time. However, the loss of control groups was high. As a result, it can be said that the skill of speaking, acquired by the method of micro teaching in foreign language, has been more permanent than the skill acquired by the traditional method.

In terms of permanence, it is aimed to determine whether there is a difference between the video and micro-education performed by video and micro-education by tape. As a result of the fourth sub-problem, there was no significant difference between the permanence of the speaking skill achieved as a result of the micro-teaching practice carried out by video and the persistence of the speaking skill reached as a result of the micro-teaching performed by tape. However, the values found reveal the view that by increasing the number of subjects, more sensitive findings can be achieved and perhaps the difference can be revealed.

The findings obtained from this study examining the effectiveness and permanence of the microteaching method and the traditional teaching method on student success in developing the pronunciation skill in foreign language seem to be similar to the findings related to microteaching that Gürkan (1991, p. 69) recorded and the findings obtained from the previous studies.

As a result of a study conducted by Krpalek in recent years (2017), it is stated that microteaching is more effective than other traditional teaching methods in terms of student success (Rashid, 2017, p.312).

However, in most studies, the Microteaching Method was carried out on 'teaching skills'. With this study, it is revealed that it is more effective than the traditional method in teaching foreign language 'pronunciation skill' as well as teaching skills. In the light of the findings revealed in the study, it was concluded that the microteaching method is more effective than the traditional teaching method in developing the pronunciation skill

in a foreign language. However, it is considered necessary to conduct other sensitive experiments on the subject.

It is expected that this study will make a different contribution in terms of showing whether the Microteaching Method can be used in the development of foreign language skills other than the development of the teaching skills.

In the light of the findings obtained in this study, the following suggestions have been developed.

- 1) In the development of students' skills related to pronunciation in a foreign language, it is possible to take advantage of both the video applied and the tape applied form of microteaching.
- 2) The methods and activities tried and developed in this study for the application of the microteaching method in the curriculum can be taken as an example by teachers to be applied in foreign language lessons.
- 3) The microteaching method, which can be used in the development of the pronunciation skill in a foreign language, can be applied to individual learning and extra-curricular activities when necessary.
- 4) The tapes and video tapes prepared for the study practices can be used as materials to improve the pronunciation skills in foreign language lessons and other tapes can be prepared for this purpose.
- 5) Other experimental studies can be conducted to test the effectiveness of the microteaching method in acquiring other skills (listening and speaking) in a foreign language.

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